

Flipped Classroom Method for the Teacher Training for Secondary Education: A Case Study in the University of Granada, Spain

<https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v14i11.9853>

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Abstract—Flipped Classroom methodology has strongly introduced in the classrooms of different educational levels, but above all in the University. This methodology could be defined as the reversal of roles in the classroom, where the student acquires theoretical knowledge outside of the classroom and becomes a space for resolving doubts and cooperative work. Thus, this paper analyzes the experience carried out at the University of Granada with students of the Master's Degree in Secondary School Training where Flipped Classroom methodology has been applied. The research methodology used is quantitative, so that an ad hoc questionnaire on a Likert scale was used to obtain the data. Among the obtained results, it is observed that the students perceive an improvement in their academic performance and the improvement of the different personal and social skills. Finally, it can be concluded that this kind of experiences where the Flipped Classroom methodology is applied favors the development of skills depending of subject taught and the field of knowledge.

Keywords—Flipped Classroom, Higher Education, ICT, Teaching Methodology.

1 Introduction

In recent years, the Flipped Classroom methodology is being implemented in the classrooms of different educational levels, which it is defined as the flipped of roles in the classroom, where the student acquires the theoretical knowledge outside and the classroom becomes a propitious space for resolving doubts and cooperative work [1, 2]. Therefore, the student previously works the contents outside the school context from the use of digital tools to develop them later in the classroom.

On the other hand, the origin of this methodology born in the concern of two teachers to oppose school absenteeism, likewise they began to record their presentations with audio to offer as support material to students [3]. From this experience they realized that this teaching method favored the development of certain benefits, among them those highlighted by the pioneers Bergmann and Sams [4] and collected in Gétrudix and Rivas [5], Zainuddin and Hajar [6] and Rincón [7]: development of a collaborative learning environment, dynamizes the role of students, actualization of

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Article submitted 2018-11-13. Resubmitted 2018-12-15. Final acceptance 2018-12-15. Final version published as submitted by the authors.